

UNDERSTANDING THE RELATIONSHIP OF LANGUAGE CULTURE AND SOCIETY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6430630>

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SamSIFL, "International language and literature" 2-course

Abstract: *Language is a mirror of the culture of a certain society, it reflects not only the real world surrounding the person, not just the actual conditions of his life, but also the social consciousness of the people, their mentality, national character and way of life, traditions, customs, morals, values, attitude, vision of the world.*

Keywords: *language, culture, society, realia, stereotype, non-verbal communication, intercultural communication.*

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, language and culture go hand in hand in various areas of scientific and practical life of society. Language is the property of each nation. Due to language, humanity has the ability to pass on its traditions, customs, and cultural values from generation to generation. Language allows each nation to be unique in relation to another nation and to create its own unique history. Culture, being the omnipotent pillar of the spiritual heritage of society, provides an opportunity for language to exist, develop and interact with other cultures, and maintain an unshakable connection with generations. Therefore, while learning a particular language as EFL students, it is necessary to get acquainted with the history, culture and inheritance of the country, in which this language received its development, transformation and enrichment.

Thus, using the methods of comparative analysis based on the researches of renowned linguists in this field as Edward T. Hall and Professor David Crystal and others, we consider the importance of the concept of communication in the study and interaction of two or more cultural-linguistic systems, intercultural non-verbal communication, cultural stereotypes, ethnographic realia and phraseological units in particular.

METHODOLOGY

As it is known, language is a constantly developing system of humankind; it is an instrument of intercultural communication, as well as a key to discoveries and knowledge, the development of science and education. According to N.V. Gogol, the greatest Russian writer of the 19th century, "our extraordinary language is still a mystery ... it is unlimited and can, alive as a life, enrich itself every minute." ("What, finally, is the essence of Russian poetry", 1846). For example, the evolution of the

English language is largely due to the fulminant development of all sectors of humankind in the modern life, such as science, electronics, medicine, industry, mechanical engineering, textile production and much more. Over the past twenty years, electronic technology has changed people's lives beyond recognition, replacing and simplifying blue-collar jobs.

Language and culture are so close that are being identified as synonyms (Scarcella, Oxford, 1992). On the one hand, language is used to express people's cultural thoughts, beliefs and to communicate; on the other hand, culture is embedded in the language. The interwoven relationship between language and culture can be summarized by Brown (2000, p.177): "A language is a part of a culture and a culture is a part of a language; the two are intricately interwoven so that one can not separate the two without losing the significance of either language or culture."

RESULTS

In 1976, Hall created a model of linguacultural substance, drawing an analogy with an iceberg. Hall believed that the culture of a society is like an iceberg, for 90% hidden under the surface and on the surface a person faces only the primary aspects that represent culture. (Beyond Culture (1976) by Edward T. Hall). Thus, in order to learn a language, it is not enough to be acquainted with the superficial aspects, it should be delved in to the origin of study, history, culture and society, which this language develops, improves and carries to the masses.

According to Singhal (1998), language teachers ought to receive both experiential and academic training, with the aim of becoming 'mediators in culture teaching.

This cultural logic, though, is achieved through 'a recognition of 'otherness', and of the limitations of one's own cultural identity' (Killick & Poveda, 1997).

According to the famous linguist and contemporary writer, David Crystal, to predict the future evolution of a language it is crucial to understand not only the present but also the past, considering the cultural background. That is precisely why it is so important to keep our eyes and ears wide open in order to know what is going on in India and China nowadays, where we notice the most significant evolution of the

English language. (Professor David Crystal, English Linguistics, Pragmatics and English Conference.)

DISCUSSION

It also has to be noted that the development of technologies has played a role in FL/FC learning since the eighties. The visual aspect of culture teaching was strengthened because the development of video technology in the eighties and computer and internet in the nineties influence FL learning and interaction in a great sense (Liaw and Johnson, 2001, Dlaska, 2000, Lin 1999, Tseng, 1999). For instance,

email communication allows a cross-culture contact possible (Liaw and Johnson, 2001) and Dlaska (2000) suggested of using internet and information technology in supporting autonomous language and culture learning.

Teaching a foreign language is based primarily on the acquaintance of students not only with the lexical, grammatical or syntactic structure of the language, but also the familiarization with the cultural component of a particular society. The practical application of various methods in teaching should become the starting point for the knowledge of the target culture, psychology, consciousness, thinking, and of course, the spirit of the whole nation.

Furthermore, in this issue, we consider the importance of the concept of communication in the study and interaction of two or more cultural-linguistic systems, in particular intercultural non-verbal communication, cultural stereotypes, ethnographic realia and phraseological units.

It goes without saying that foreign language teachers should be foreign culture teachers, having the ability to experience and analyze both the home and target cultures (Byram, Morgan et al., 1994: 73).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the language is a well of culture of a certain society, which contains all the beauty, wealth, traditions, customs, morals, values, attitude, the way of life of entire generations, art and literature, the outlook of the entire people. Language as a mirror reflects not only the real world surrounding the person, not just the actual conditions of his life, but also the social consciousness of the people, national character, national psychology, spirituality, their mentality, vision of the world.

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